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Chemical Investigation of the Leaves of *Phlogacanthus thyrsiflorus*

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*PHLOGACANTHUS thyrsiflorus*¹ (family Acanthaceae) is used medicinally like *Adhatoda vasica* which has been reported to be expectorant and mild bronchial antiseptic². The present communication reports the isolation of β -sitosterol, lupeol and betulin from the leaves of *P. thyrsiflorus*.

The petroleum ether (b.p. 60-80°) extract of the air-dried leaves of *P. thyrsiflorus* on column chromatography over silica gel furnished three compounds designated as compounds A, B and C.

Compound A: $C_{29}H_{50}O$ (M^+ 414), m.p. 136-37° (EtOH), $[\alpha]_D^{25} - 35.6$ ($CHCl_3$), gave a violet to green colour in the Lieberman-Burchard test indicating it to be a phytosterol. On heating with acetic anhydride and pyridine on steam bath it yielded an acetate, $C_{31}H_{52}O_2$ (M^+ 456) m.p. 127-28°, $[\alpha]_D^{25} - 41.4$ ($CHCl_3$). The identity of compound A with β -sitosterol was confirmed by

comparison of m.p., m.m.p., optical rotation and TLC with an authentic sample.

Compound B: $C_{30}H_{50}O$ (M^+ 426), m.p. 211-12°. It gave a violet to pink colour in the Lieberman-Burchard test indicating it to be a terpenoid. On heating with acetic anhydride and pyridine on steam bath it yielded a monoacetate, $C_{32}H_{52}O_2$ (M^+ 468), m.p. 213-15°, $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 41.7$ ($CHCl_3$). The identities of compound B and its acetate with lupeol and its acetate respectively were established by comparison (m.p., m.m.p., TLC and IR) with authentic samples.

Compound C: $C_{30}H_{50}O_2$ (M^+ 442), m.p. 258°. It showed violet-pink colour in the Lieberman-Burchard test. Its mass spectral fragmentation pattern was found to be very similar to that of betulin³. On heating with acetic anhydride and pyridine on steam bath it furnished a diacetate, $C_{34}H_{54}O_4$ (M^+ 526) m.p. 222°. Compound C was identified as betulin by comparison of m.p., m.m.p., TLC and IR spectra with an authentic sample of betulin.

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